

COP II

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What is COP II?

is a coatomer

transfers proteins from the rough endoplasmic reticulum to the golgi apparatus.

"COPII" refers to the specific coat protein complex that initiates the budding process.

COP-II's coat is composed of five proteins:

- Sar1
- Sec23
- Sec24
- Sec13
- Sec31

These proteins dimerize to form larger protein complexes:

- 1) Sec23p/Sec24p Heterodimer
- 2) Sec13p/Sec31p Heterotetramer

COP-II Coat Components

Protein	Size
Sar1p	21 kDa
Sec12p	43 kDa
Sec23-complex	400 kDa
Sec23p	85 kDa
Sec24p	105 kDa
Sec13-complex	700 kDa
Sec13p	34 kDa
Sec31p	150 kDa

“Sec” refers to secretory mutants in yeast develop by Randy Schekman.

Coat Assembly

- 1) GDP-Sar1p binds to Sec12p
- 2) GTP/GDP exchange
- 3) GTP-Sar1p anchors to membrane

Budding process Assembly of COPII vesicles can be summarized as:

1. Sar1-GDP interacts with the ER transmembrane protein Sec12.
2. Sar1-GTP recruits Sec23/Sec24 coat protein to form a pre-budding complex.
3. Pre-budding complex (composed of Sar1-GTP bound with Sec23/24) recruits Sec13/Sec31, which forms the second coat layer.
4. Sec13/Sec31 complex forms a cage-like outer coat (similar to the formation of clathrin vesicles).

Sar1p is a GTPase that acts as a "switch" that flips between an activated membrane embedded GTP-bound form, and an inactive soluble GDP-bound form.

Sec12, a transmembrane protein found in the ER acts as a Guanine nucleotide exchange factor by stimulating the release of GDP to allow the binding of GTP in Sar1.

Membrane-bound Sar1p recruits the Sec23p/24p complex to form what is collectively known as the pre-budding complex.

Pre-budding complex (composed of Sar1-GTP and Sec23/24) recruits the flexible Sec13p/31p complex, characterized by polymerization of the Sec13/31 complex with other Sec13/31 complexes to form a cuboctahedron with a broader lattice than its Clathrin vesicle analog.

Some proteins are found to be responsible for selectively packaging cargos into COPII vesicles.

When the COPII vesicle is in close proximity to the Cis-Golgi membrane, it sheds its coat and the components are recycled to function for another vesicle.

Conformational changes

CopII has three
specific binding
sites that can each
be complexed

Cellular component

COPII-coated vesicle The membrane surrounding a COPII-coated vesicle.

COPII-coated vesicles mediate the vesicular transport of cargo such as proteins.

COPII-coated vesicles are believed to bud from the endoplasmic reticulum and be involved in the anterograde transport between the ER to Golgi.

Schematic depiction of secretory membrane traffic pathways. Vesicular traffic pathways from the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) to vesicular-tubular clusters (VTCs), to and within the Golgi complex, to the endosome/lysosome system and to the plasma membrane are indicated (simplified scheme). Transport between the ER and the cis -Golgi is regulated by the COP II and COP I vesicle coats. VTCs vesicular-tubular clusters. PM plasma membrane. For details see text.

(A) Purified COP II vesicles produced in vitro in an incubation with the non-hydrolyzable GTP-analogue GMP-PNP.
(B) Immuno-staining on a cryosection (68 400) of a COP II vesicle pellet with an antibody against Sar1p.
(A) and (B) are reproduced with permission from Barlowe et al . (1994), *Cell* , 77, 895-907. (C) Physical arrangement of ER exit sites and the Golgi complex in mammalian cells and a yeast.

GTPase activation and membrane binding

priming complex formation

coat oligomerization and loss of the GTPase

vesicle budding

(A) and (B) Localization of the COP I coat by immunoelectron microscopy on GTP-g-S-treated rat liver Golgi fractions.
(C) Golgi cisternae.

Vesicular transfer involves germination, detachment of the veneer, docking on the target membrane, and attachment.

Vesicles that germinate from membranes usually have a specific protein coating on their cytosolic surface that:

- The membrane sprouts
- Helps trap molecules inside the vesicle.

germination and attachment of a vesicle

The formation of the SNARE complex causes vesicular adhesion.

A. Clathrin triskelion

B. Clathrin coat architecture

C. CCV composition

In the first step, the Sar1 monomeric protein G binds to the membrane by nucleotide exchange. In the second step, the COPII coating components are mounted. After separation from the source membrane, Sar1 performs GTP hydrolysis in step 3, so in step 4, the coating components are separated from the vesicle. Nucleotide exchange and GTP hydrolysis by Sar1 are regulated by Sec12 and Sec23 proteins, respectively.

Sar1 calls COPII-coated proteins to the membrane to form vesicles. This coating contains a variety of proteins, including Sec23 and Sec24. Different vesicle proteins are also formed as a mass or as a marker-dependent interaction in specific vesicles.

References:

- [Pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov)
- <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/imbc20>
- <https://article.tebyan.net/353899/%D8%A7%D9%86%D8%A%D9%82%D8%A7%D9%84-%D9%88%D8%B2%DB%8C%DA%A9%D9%88%D9%84%DB%8C-%D8%A8%D8%AE%D8%B4-%D8%A7%D9%88%D9%84>